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- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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Abstract:	This deliverable shortly describes the project’s corporate identity, including its logo, and the initial set-up of the INERRANT project’s public website.
Keyword List:	Project website, public website, visibility, communication, dissemination, information, outreach, logo, Corporate Identity

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Executive Summary

This document describes the activities conducted under the INERRANT project to **the public INERRANT website**. The project activities will be implemented in line with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

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1. Introduction

Providing information about INERRANT’s goals and work as well as the results achieved in the course of the project is of utmost importance to foster the project’s success. Raising awareness about the project is better achieved if a “corporate identity” for the project is established from the start, and the way information is provided to stakeholders outside the consortium is unified. A corporate identity has therefore been prepared within the scope of Work Package 7 “Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation”. It will be used for all communication and dissemination materials of INERRANT.

The INERRANT public website is the project’s predominant tool for communication about the project and, in the end, for disseminating results aiming at reaching a broad public as well as stakeholders and scientists in the field and creating continuous awareness of the project’s activities.

Moreover, INERRANT is part of the broader cluster under the CSA Batteries 2030+ initiative (<https://battery2030.eu/>), which coordinates dissemination activities for related projects. Battery 2030+ brings together the most important stakeholders in the field of battery research and development to work on concrete actions that support the implementation of the European Green Deal, the UN Sustainable Development Goals, as well as the European Action plan on Batteries and the European SET-plan.

INERRANT’s link will be included on the CSA Batteries 2030+ website. This integration will significantly enhance the visibility and accessibility of the project’s outputs and updates. By being featured on the CSA platform, the website will benefit from increased exposure to relevant stakeholders and the broader community, facilitating better outreach and engagement.

2. Description of Activities

2.1 Corporate Identity

A coherent and well-developed corporate identity has several advantages from which the INERRANT project can benefit. In addition to visualizing the project’s professional nature, it ensures internal and external consistency and a quick recognition when the project is presented.

A logo and a colour scheme brand the INERRANT project as a distinctive and recognizable research project. A professionally designed project logo (Figure 1) with a corresponding colour scheme (Figure 2) creates a unique corporate identity of the project. The logo consists of a textual and visual part to ensure that it is better understood, recognised and remembered.

Figure 1 INERRANT Logo

Dark green 27/20/100

Light Green 168/207/57

Light blue 25/187/103

Figure 2 INERRANT colour code

2.2 Public INERRANT Website

The INERRANT website is directed at the general public as well as different stakeholders with an interest in the project, its activities as well as its outcomes, innovations and progress. Such stakeholders include the scientific and educational community but also start-ups, Industry, Regulatory Bodies and policy makers.

For its launch, the website offers a project introduction including the approach and key facts of INERRANT. In addition, it offers background information about the research and the consortium members. There is also a section on project-related news and events and links to INERRANT social media channels on LinkedIn and X. Finally, contact details, imprint and a privacy statement are included.

The different sections are available in the tabs in the main navigation with drop-down menus to subpages.

The project website currently offers the following main features and information (provided as screenshots in the annex):

- (1) Home: Main page and entry point to the INERRANT website providing a short intro, a banner with latest news and links to other parts of the website;
- (2) About: Learning about the core objective of INERRANT as well as key messages about the project;
- (3) Research: Includes the approach & mission of INERRANT as well as key facts; The research section has four sub-sites regarding:
 - a. Objectives
 - b. Approach
 - c. Work Packages
 - d. Impact
- (4) Team: Presentation of the INERRANT partner institutions and their teams, as well as the work packages and an interactive description;
- (5) News & Events: Frequently updated section with news and events from within the consortium and generated from subject-related content;

Some new sections may be added over the project's development as the first results as well as the impact of the project on the external stakeholders, for instance through media coverage, become apparent.

The public website is online since 27/07/2024. It has been developed by a professional communications team at EURICE together with the coordinator FORTH and feedback from all partners. The website can be accessed via <https://inerrant-batteries.eu/>.

3. Conclusions

The website as well as the social media accounts LinkedIn and X are online and ready to inform the interested user about the project. They are in line with the project's corporate identity. The set-up ensures that the website is appealing, efficient and easy to use. Since the development of the website is a continuous task, the website as presented in this deliverable must be considered to only be a

‘snapshot’. Content will be regularly updated. Additional information and subpages will be introduced in the course of the project.

4. Annexes – Screenshots of the website

Figure 3 INERRANT Homepage screenshot

Figure 4 INERRANT About section

Figure 5 INERRANT Objectives

Figure 6 INERRANT Approach

Figure 7 INERRANT Work Packages

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